

(REVIEW ARTICLE)

Knowledge and personal hygiene behavior during menstruation among adolescent girls in various regions: A literature review

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World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews, 2024, 22(02), 864–869

Publication history: Received on 30 March 2024; revised on 11 May 2024; accepted on 13 May 2024

Article DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/wjarr.2024.22.2.1335>

Abstract

Personal hygiene is still a public health issue in Indonesia. Menstrual hygiene is the management of hygiene and health when women experience menstruation as part of a personal hygiene care routine with the concept of clean. Personal hygiene during menstruation plays an important role in a person's health status in avoiding functional disorders of the reproductive organs. Knowledge in Indonesia states that poor personal hygiene behavior during menstruation of adolescent girls is a major concern because it has a health impact. The method used was literature review by searching articles through Google Scholar and Pubmed databases. Selection stages were carried out to obtain articles that met the inclusion and exclusion criteria, and 6 articles were obtained that could be analyzed. The results showed that knowledge has a significant role in determining menstrual hygiene behavior in adolescent girls, there are also differences in knowledge and behavior when performing personal hygiene behavior during menstruation in urban and rural areas. To improve knowledge and behavior of personal hygiene during menstruation, especially in various regions, it can be done with various strategies such as promotion, education, collaboration, improving service quality, and increasing accessibility.

Keywords: Menstrual Hygiene; Knowledge; Behavior; Adolescents

1. Introduction

Menstruation is a physiological event for women who experience a critical change in their normal life [17]. It is characterized by the release of the uterine lining and the discharge of blood from the vagina. Critical changes that occur include biological or physical, psychological, and social changes that make adolescent girls need to pay attention to reproductive organ hygiene. Menstruation is a sign of sexual maturity in women and usually begins during puberty. According to the Basic Health Research conducted by the Ministry of Health in 2018, 11.7% of adolescents in Indonesia experience irregular menstruation. There are previous studies mentioning that personal hygiene provides challenges for adolescent girls who experience menstruation [13].

Personal hygiene is still a public health problem in Indonesia. In general, personal hygiene consists of various aspects, namely hand hygiene, clean clothes, personal health and behavior [5]. Especially by adolescent girls, personal hygiene is needed because adolescent girls experience menstruation. Personal hygiene during menstruation is often called menstrual hygiene. Menstrual hygiene is part of personal hygiene. Menstrual hygiene is the management of hygiene and health when women experience menstruation as part of a personal hygiene care routine with a clean concept [20]. Menstrual hygiene plays an important role in a person's health status in avoiding functional disorders of the reproductive organs [10]. Maintaining good personal hygiene behavior during menstruation is important to prevent infection and maintain health during menstruation. Personal hygiene during menstruation aims to avoid viruses, bacteria and germs, and prevent the spread of disease from one person to another. So that during menstruation, avoid

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reproductive tract infections [4]. Globally, many women and girls face difficulties in managing their menstrual personal hygiene [3]. In several previous studies, it was mentioned that personal hygiene behavior during menstruation is still relatively poor, especially in adolescent girls. Knowledge in Indonesia states that poor personal hygiene behavior during menstruation of adolescent girls is a major concern because it has a health impact. There are several factors that influence personal hygiene behavior during menstruation. Knowledge has a significant role in determining menstrual hygiene behavior in adolescent girls.

2. Material and methods

This research uses a descriptive qualitative approach, where this method utilizes qualitative data that is described descriptively. Data sources in this study were obtained directly from references such as journals, books, and other written sources. The data collection technique in this research uses literature review techniques or literature studies conducted to collect valid, complete, and relevant information related to the topic of the problem that is the object of research. Literature review is a scientific study that focuses on one particular topic. Literature review will provide an overview of the development of a particular topic. Literature review will allow a researcher to identify a theory or method, develop a theory or method, identify gaps that occur between a theory and its relevance in the field or to a research result [2; 13]. The selection stage is carried out to obtain articles that match the inclusion and exclusion criteria, so 6 articles can be analyzed. Searches were conducted in the Google Scholar and Pubmed databases published in the period 2018 to 2023. At the initial stage, 1,200 results were found in Google Scholar and 279 results in Pubmed with the keywords "personal hygiene during menstruation in adolescent girls", "knowledge and behavior of personal hygiene during menstruation", and "personal hygiene during menstruation in adolescent girls". Then next, articles were selected based on compatibility with the discussion in this study, so 10 articles with the theme "Knowledge and Behavior of Personal hygiene during Menstruation" were obtained. Then the last step, these 10 articles were further identified by filtering the relevance of the article content to the focus of this research. So that 6 articles were used for literature review in this study.

3. Results and discussion

Based on the results of the literature search, there were 6 articles that fit the criteria. Differences in knowledge and personal hygiene behavior during menstruation among adolescent girls in various regions with several indicators, including those that have been collected based on several previous studies as follows:

Table 1 List of article

Author	Title of Research	Method	Sample/Population	Result
Yadav et al. [21]	Knowledge, Attitude, and Practice on Menstrual hygiene Management among School Adolescents	Cross Sectional	The sample in the study was 276 seventh and eighth grade students from 11 schools. Self-administered questionnaires were used to obtain information from school students. Descriptive analysis was conducted to analyze the knowledge, attitudes and practices of school adolescents on menstrual hygiene management.	The implementation in Doti City, Western Nepal stated that 67.4% of respondents had sufficient knowledge and 26.4% of respondents had good knowledge about menstrual hygiene management. However, out of 141 adolescent girl respondents, only 56 (40%) practiced good menstrual hygiene. About half of the respondents had a positive attitude towards issues related to menstrual hygiene management.
Sitohang et al. [15]	Health Education on Menstrual Health Management on Knowledge And Attitude of Adolescents of Private Madrasah	Case Control	The sample in this study were seventh grade students as many as 36 people, using the total sampling technique.	In the implementation at MTS Amal Saleh, health education activities were carried out using video education media, leaflets and modules. The results showed that the knowledge of adolescents about menstrual health management after attending health education was

	Tsanawiyah Amal Saleh			mostly good (88.9%) and their attitudes were all positive.
Khatib et al. [6]	Relationship between Knowledge, Attitude, and Personal hygiene Behavior with Vaginitis Symptoms in Female Students of SMPN 1 Padang City dan SMPN 23 Padang.	Cross Sectional	The population in this study were students in grades VII, VII, and IX of SMPN 1 and SMPN 23 Padang and the sample in this study was 120 students.	In the implementation of the SMPN 1 Padang and SMPN 23 Padang program, it was found that the level of knowledge of respondents at SMPN 1 Padang was higher (average = 6.14) compared to respondents at SMPN 23 Padang (average = 5.84). So, it was concluded that the relationship between personal hygiene knowledge and vaginitis symptoms in SMPN 23 Padang students but there was no relationship between SMPN 1 Padang students.
Purnama. [11]	Knowledge and Personal Hygiene Actions during Menstruation in Adolescents.	Cross Sectional	The population in the study were adolescent girls in class XI majoring in Nursing at SMKN 4 Negara, Jembrana Regency, Bali with inclusion criteria: already menarch. The sample size was 42 female students through simple random sampling technique. Knowledge and practice were measured using a questionnaire.	In the implementation at SMKN 4 Negara, Jembrana Regency, Bali, it was stated that most of the adolescent girls had good knowledge. When viewed from whether or not they have received information, most of them have received information, the source of information also varies from health workers or social media. The majority of female students also have good personal hygiene actions during menstruation. The students were majoring in nursing where in class XI they had received lessons on personal hygiene even though it was not specific to personal hygiene during menstruation.
Amanda and Fajar [1]	Adolescent Menstrual Hygiene Behavior: a Study on Female Students in a Modern Boarding School in Depok City.	Cross Sectional	The study population was students of grade 8 and 9 of Madrasah Tsanawiyah education level and grade 10 and 11 of Madrasah Aliyah education level in the 2019-2020 academic year, totaling 135 students. The sample in this study was 77 female students who were determined by simple random sampling method with a sampling frame derived from the attendance data of female students. Samples were selected with inclusion criteria including female students who have experienced menarche and are willing to become research respondents.	In the implementation at the Modern Islamic Boarding School in Depok City, it was said that most respondents had poor menstrual hygiene behavior. There is a relationship between attitude, belief in myths, ustadzah support, and information exposure with the menstrual hygiene behavior of female students. Attitude factors, belief in myths, ustadzah support, and information exposure have a very important role in improving good menstrual hygiene behavior in female students.
Utami and Yeni [19]	Personal Hygiene Behavior of Adolescent Girls During Menstruation at SMPN 1 Masaran.	Case Control	The population in this study were seventh grade students as many as 159 students, a sample of 36 students with accidental sampling technique.	Implementation at SMPN 1 Masaran, it was mentioned that based on the behavior group of the respondents studied, most of them were sufficient as many as 18 people (51.4) and a small portion was lacking as many as 8 people (22.9%). This is evidenced

				by the respondent's source of information which states that based on the group of information sources regarding personal hygiene during menstruation from the respondents studied, most of them are mothers as many as 33 people (94%) and a small portion of fathers as many as 1 person (3%).
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The results of research on the implementation of personal hygiene behavior during menstruation, especially on knowledge related to the sources of information obtained, stated that information can be obtained from anywhere to gain knowledge related to personal hygiene during menstruation, so that they can apply it in the practice of taking care of themselves during menstruation. The results of this study are in line with research conducted by Suryani (2019) that information provision affects personal hygiene behavior during menstruation [16]. by getting information through teachers during school lessons, students practice it in their daily lives. One of the driving factors that materialize health behavior is through references from community behavior [10]. The reference can be from the teacher. Knowledge has a significant role in determining menstrual hygiene behavior in adolescent girls. The one results of research showed a relationship between knowledge and personal hygiene actions during menstruation with a positive relationship direction and moderate relationship strength, meaning that the higher the knowledge score, the better the personal hygiene actions [7]. These results are in line with research conducted by that there is a relationship between adolescent girls' knowledge about menarche and menstruation with personal hygiene practices during menstruation [8].

There are also several things that cause knowledge related to personal hygiene behavior during menstruation, namely sources of information, including in research which states that sources of information on personal hygiene behavior during menstruation at school can be obtained from teachers [7], while in another research states that sources of information can be obtained from mothers [19]. Sources of information related to personal hygiene during menstruation can also be obtained from health workers or social media. Then the media also influences knowledge to behave personal hygiene during menstruation, as in the research stated that media is an important thing to increase knowledge in personal hygiene behavior during menstruation, and the media in this study is booklet media, and the results obtained there are differences in the knowledge of adolescent girls related to hygiene in menstruation before and after being given booklet media [12]. Location factors can affect a person's level of knowledge of personal hygiene during menstruation. Another research showed that external genitalia hygiene was low among adolescents in urban areas, 58.09% and 79.45% in rural areas [18]. This is inversely proportional to the research was conducted in Malaysia, stating that the level of knowledge of respondents regarding personal hygiene in the city was higher than those living in the suburbs. This is also in line with research that residents in the city are 1.8 times higher in knowledge about menstrual hygiene management in the suburbs.

To improve knowledge and behavior of personal hygiene during menstruation, especially in various regions, it can be done with various strategies such as promotion, education, collaboration, improving service quality, and increasing accessibility by means of:

1. Promotion: Can conduct health awareness campaigns on discussing menstruation and removing the stigma that may be associated with it. These campaigns could include seminars, workshops, or the use of social media to disseminate information. It can also be through social media, brochures, banners, or advertisements in the mass media. When promoting, make it easy to understand and appropriate to the local language and culture. Use adequate illustrations and resources to convey the message clearly.
2. Education: Schools can provide comprehensive sexual and reproductive health education, including education on menstruation, body anatomy, the menstrual cycle, and the importance of personal care during menstruation.
3. Collaboration: Schools can collaborate with relevant parties, such as community groups, health organizations, or government agencies to improve knowledge in personal hygiene behavior of adolescent girls. Schools should also support adolescent girls by providing adequate facilities such as toilets and hand washing stations. They can also provide a safe space for girls to change pads or tampons.
4. Improved service quality: Ensure easy and affordable access to menstrual health products such as pads, tampons, or menstrual cups. This is especially important in areas that may have limited access.
5. Increased accessibility: This could be by organizing a public health observance to celebrate World Menstrual Day or a similar event to raise awareness about the importance of menstrual health education. families can also be involved in menstruation education. Families can help their children feel comfortable talking about menstrual issues and provide support.

4. Conclusion

There are various sources of information that can be obtained to gain knowledge about personal hygiene during menstruation, including family, teachers, peers, social media, health workers, and many others. Media is also influential in the knowledge of personal hygiene behavior during menstruation, and there are location factors that can affect a person's level of knowledge of personal hygiene management, especially during menstruation. So it can be concluded that there is a significant relationship between knowledge and menstrual hygiene behavior among adolescent girls in various regions of Indonesia. Adolescent girls who have good knowledge and awareness about menstrual hygiene are more likely to implement good menstrual hygiene practices. However, the prevalence of menstrual hygiene among adolescent girls in Indonesia is still relatively poor, and many of them experience challenges related to menstrual hygiene.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

Article Information

This article did not receive assistance from the government, private companies, or non-profit organizations.

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